

Enhancing Health Risk Monitoring: An Explainable Human-Centric Approach Using Wearable Data and Sensor Integration

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Abstract. This paper presents the development of an Explainable AI (XAI) approach designed for first responders (FRs) to monitor and predict health risks based on real-time data from wearable devices. The tool integrates Machine Learning models to analyze vital signs, such as heart rate, respiratory rate, and skin temperature, providing predictions for conditions like exhaustion, stress levels, and respiratory issues. To ensure transparency and trustworthiness, the tool incorporates XAI techniques, including SHAP and LIME, offering clear and interpretable explanations for the model's predictions. The main goal of this research is to introduce to the users the capabilities of integrated XAI in real-time monitoring, alert generation, and interactive visualizations, enhancing first responders' ability to make informed decisions in high-stress environments, as well as highlighting important vitals as features to be implemented in wearable technologies. Additionally, the tool adheres to strict data privacy regulations and is designed for scalability and seamless integration with existing monitoring systems. This innovative approach, as part of this project, aims to improve the safety and efficiency of first responders by providing actionable insights and transparent explanations of health risks.

Keywords: Explainable AI · Machine Learning · Wearable Sensors · First Responders.

1 Introduction

The tremendous technological advances in the development and usage of wearable devices have achieved remarkably high growth rates in the last few years. Wearable devices that collect diverse biosignals from individuals have been extensively researched, highlighting the challenges and opportunities in their design, as well as in the resulting biosignal analysis and interpretation. These advances

in wearable technology drive research and development efforts, leading to the use of wearable devices to monitor, analyze, and interpret data for various healthcare applications. The integration of wearable technology into various sectors, including the medical domain, has led to significant advancements in health monitoring and emergency response. In the medical field, such integration can lead to more effective patient monitoring and timely interventions.

The use of wearables leads to the collection of diverse data streams, encompassing both physiological and environmental metrics, which are crucial for comprehensive monitoring. This research project focuses on XAI (eXplainable Artificial Intelligence) wearables, designed to enhance situation awareness by continuously monitoring vital signs and generating clear, explainable alerts to the users. By capturing essential health metrics such as heart rate, blood pressure, and oxygen saturation, these devices provide critical data for health monitoring. Additionally, they aim to fuse this physiological information with environmental indicators, such as atmospheric gas levels, in order to offer a more comprehensive situational assessment during emergency situations. The fusion of multimodal data—combining physiological and environmental information—offers a more holistic view of the situation at hand, which is crucial for making accurate and timely decisions in critical scenarios. Furthermore, the need for explainability in AI-driven systems is paramount; it ensures that the insights and alerts generated by these wearables are transparent and understandable to users. By providing clear explanations for the data patterns and anomalies detected, XAI analysis on wearables’ data can help users, especially healthcare professionals and first responders, to accurately and effectively act upon the system’s recommendations, while also increasing their trust in the system’s capabilities and reasoning. This transparency is vital in high-stress environments where rapid and well-informed decision-making can significantly impact the outcome and health of an individual.

For our research project, which focuses on XAI wearables and their role in enhancing situation awareness, our contributions towards the field of emergency response and health monitoring can be summarized as follows:

- **Multi-Output Model Explanations:** Our research proposes a novel approach for explaining the outputs of multi-output regression models derived from wearable sensor data. By employing explainable artificial intelligence techniques, we aim to provide transparent and interpretable explanations for the predictions of various health parameters.
- **Evaluation of Different XAI Techniques:** We conducted an evaluation of various eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) techniques, including LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations), SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), and surrogate models.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Initially, background information and key concepts relevant to XAI and wearables are presented, as well as related literature and work concerning the usage of Explainable AI in medical datasets containing vital signs. We then provide a detailed explanation of the motivation behind our work, including current challenges and the need for

explainability in medical emergency situations. Next, our methodology is thoroughly presented, by describing the main architecture that we followed, focusing on the explainability aspect of our work. Finally, we conclude this paper by discussing our conclusions, alongside potential ideas that would expand our work in the future.

2 Background and Related work

2.1 Wearables Data

Real-time data collection and analysis, through wearable physiological monitoring devices, can be used to assess a person's health and performance. The need for this assessment is particularly crucial when we are referring to first responders, who are frequently exposed to high physical, mental, and emotional stress levels when working in high-risk austere environments [12]. Additionally, this technology can be utilized for faster recovery and better performance in intense activities [23]. Research shows that physiological monitoring of workers with wearables also helps with the observation of several health risks [3]. The frequency of behaviors described as stressful in a self-assessment psychometric questionnaire correlated with the classification accuracy of stressful occurrences that used Heart Rate Variation (HRV) parameters of ECG recordings[15]. Concerning first responders, using thermoregulatory modeling and physiological monitoring as non-invasive techniques could enhance law enforcement's efforts to lower the risk of heat-related sickness or injury [14]. The implementation of continuous field monitoring for firefighters may offer novel insights into the relationship between their unique work environment and elevated cardiac risks[4]. Even for dehydration, which is a challenging prediction, it is possible to use medical wearable data for hydration monitoring and to forecast the last time someone drank water, so those who work in extremely hot or cold temperatures can receive reminders to stay hydrated [20].

2.2 Situation Awareness

Situation Awareness involves the understanding of the environment and how it changes over time or in response to other factors. It is a critical component in effective and efficient decision-making, especially in critical situations such as Mass Casualty Incidents (MCIs). During an MCI, the capacity of resources is often depleted, leading to chaotic management and rapid decision-making taken under extreme pressure. Over time, MCIs are becoming more frequent [11], affecting millions of lives, particularly in developing countries. In order to enhance and assist MCI management, Information and Communications Technology (ICT) has the potential to play a critical role [17]. ICT provides numerous benefits in these scenarios, such as real-time data and alerts, which can aid decision-making processes to a great extent. As already highlighted in previous research [1], AI is essential for disaster management across all its phases: mitigation, preparedness,

response, and recovery, leading to faster and more effective handling of critical situations. Specifically, AI and Machine Learning models can identify patterns and predict future incidents, assist in time-critical tasks that arise in such situations, such as patient triage, as well as provide crucial support to emergency personnel in their decisions. The use of AI-based systems and solutions in the effective management of MCIs has been a topic of research in recent years [16], with various solutions being proposed. One exemplary AI system that automates primary triage classification is the ARTEMIS framework [10]. This system aims to assist first responders of MCIs by using a robot that can accurately identify patients, measure their vitals, and assign an appropriate triage acuity level.

2.3 Explainable AI methods

We will now explore two popular model-agnostic XAI techniques, SHAP and LIME, which are commonly used to provide an interpretability layer in Machine Learning models. Model-agnostic techniques are flexible methods that can be applied to any Machine Learning model, regardless of its structure, leading to their widespread adoption. SHAP and LIME are widely used not only to enhance the transparency of Machine Learning models, but also to assist in the decision-making process in various fields, including the medical domain.

SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) [13] is an XAI technique based on cooperative game theory, which aims to measure the contribution of each input feature in a prediction. SHAP assigns an importance value to each feature for a particular prediction, by approximating the Shapley values from game theory. This involves calculating the difference in the model’s prediction with and without each feature. The resulting SHAP values provide an insight into the influence of each feature, which in turn provides a locally accurate explanation to the user. Additionally, by aggregating multiple such explanations across a dataset, SHAP can provide a global explanation regarding the importance of each input feature.

LIME (Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations) [18] is another popular explainability technique, which generates a local explanation for each instance. Similar to SHAP, it provides the importance of each input feature as output. The approach taken by LIME is based on a surrogate model, which is a simpler and more transparent model that is trained to replicate the behavior of the original complex black box model. Specifically, given a test case x , a linear model is trained and used to provide a locally faithful explanation. For each sample x , the surrogate model is trained on a dataset consisting of numerous drawn samples in the vicinity of x , created by randomly perturbing x in the feature space. With this approach, even though the surrogate model will not be able to globally approximate the original model due to its simplistic linear nature, it will be able to provide a faithful local explanation for each sample.

2.4 Explainable AI in healthcare

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) has gained significant traction in the medical domain, particularly for enhancing the transparency and trustworthi-

ness of Machine Learning models, as well as identifying key vitals that have a major impact on the model predictions. Research has mainly been focused on in-hospital care, using vital signs gathered from patients at admission or during their stay. For example, Tsiklidis et al. used data obtained from the National Trauma Data Bank (NTDB), a US trauma dataset, in order to predict the survival probabilities of trauma patients at hospital admission [24]. Primary vital signs such as heart and respiratory rate were used to train a Machine Learning classifier. Using SHAP values, the importance of each input feature was calculated in individual patient records, examining both correct as well as incorrect model prediction cases. The SHAP technique was also used by Gonzalez et al., who utilized vital sign measurements and lab results from the popular MIMIC-III dataset for mortality rate prediction [6]. In this case, SHAP values were used to identify the most important features for the prediction, as well as establish critical threshold values for each feature, in order to improve the configuration of the ICU alarm that warns medical personnel. Finally, Falsetti et al. used explainability to identify risk factors for therapeutic failure and in-hospital occurrences of stroke and major bleeding, in patients with a history of atrial fibrillation who were admitted to a hospital for critical illness [5]. The LIME method was used to provide local explanations, while key input features that had a major impact at a global level were also identified.

Related literature regarding pre-hospital care and data also exists, where vital signs gathered from wrist and chest wearables are used to predict medical conditions such as stress and fatigue. For example, Banerjee et al. used heart rate variability features obtained from the WESAD dataset, to predict mental stress levels in individuals [2]. SHAP values were used to generate feature importance explanations, at both local and global levels, as well as to find global relationships between each feature and the model predictions. Similar work on stress detection using the WESAD dataset was also performed by Jaber et al. [8]. In this case, apart from the impact of each input feature, additional information was collected into an explanatory AI report for each case, which was evaluated by medical experts. The report contains the output stress probability of the model, a value interval for each feature under non-stress conditions, as well as flags for potentially abnormal values in features. Apart from stress detection, XAI using data collected from wearables has also been used to identify dehydration. For example, Sabry et al. used SHAP values in order to determine the most important physiological and environmental metrics for hydration monitoring, using data from multiple sensors, including respiratory rate, galvanic skin response, and surrounding temperature [21].

3 Key Concepts and Motivation

Horizon Europe projects for disaster response seek to design and develop integrated toolkits, at the service of response agencies, which will be used for enhanced situational awareness and management during complex incidents. To this end, our work, aims to promote a trustable warning, alerts, and notifications sys-

tem. To achieve this, AI algorithms will be imbued with explainable capabilities, producing human-centered explanations, which will enable users to better understand the AI systems and their outputs. These project aim to raise the standards of situation awareness during critical events where first response is needed, by increasing the accuracy and reliability of health risk alerting. Moreover, putting such integration into practice lessens the workload for the command room, which fosters improved efficiency in disaster resilience systems. Additionally, reliable AI systems uphold moral standards and regulatory compliance, streamline treatment processes, and assist in cutting down costs and time needed to successfully deal with critical situations. Lastly, it encourages improved global stakeholder interaction, which facilitates the flow of knowledge through related research advancements, leading to better and more effective solutions in the future.

Figure 1 illustrates the process of deciphering individual predictions. It is evident that when given detailed information, a control room operator is in a far better position to make an informed decision, with the aid of an AI system. In this instance, a brief list of input features with weights indicating their impact on the system—symptoms that either support the prediction or provide evidence against it—serves as an explanation provided to the end user, alongside the model’s prediction. Given their prior knowledge of the application area, humans can typically accept (trust) or reject predictions, if they are able to comprehend the underlying logic that led to the prediction. For instance, it has been shown that providing explanations to end users can boost the acceptance of automated systems [7].

Fig. 1: A model predicts that a FR is suffering from high stress levels, with the explainable method highlighting the FR’s vitals and measurements that led to this prediction. Two features, humidity and step count, are portrayed as major contributors to the prediction, while temperature is considered to be insignificant by the system. Through this explanation, the control room can make an informed decision about whether to trust the model’s prediction.

4 Methodology

This section summarizes the methods used in our research to enhance situation awareness through explanations. Our methodology follows a four-step block architecture: (i) Data Sources, (ii) Machine Learning Models, (iii) Explanations

Layer, and (iv) User Evaluation. The initial stage involves the collection of multimodal data from various wearable sensors, capturing physiological and environmental information. Alternatively, the facilitation of existing datasets will be an option for our research. The next block addresses the development and training of Machine Learning models, in order to predict multiple health risks. The third step involves applying different XAI techniques, including popular methods such as LIME and SHAP, to create an explainability layer that provides transparent and interpretable insights into the model’s predictions, and visualize them in a clear way to the user. Finally, we conduct user evaluations with first responders and healthcare professionals to assess the effectiveness and usability of the ex-

Fig. 2: Workflow of the proposed approach.

plained alerts in improving decision-making during emergencies. The flow of our methodology is depicted in Figure 2.

In this study, we propose a comprehensive set of sensors for advanced wearable devices aimed at real-time health monitoring. While we have not yet commenced data collection, our initial work will leverage open wearable datasets, as seen in Table 1, to validate our approach. Our wearables are equipped with sensors to monitor a wide range of physiological parameters, including respiration rate, SpO2 (blood oxygen saturation), heart rate, and heart rate variability, which are all crucial for assessing cardiovascular and respiratory health. Additionally, the integrated IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) provides detailed motion analysis, while sensors for body core and skin temperature offer insights into thermal regulation. Regarding the raw data collection, the baseline determination should be in normal conditions and during training sessions of the FRs. Furthermore, feedback will be collected regarding the use of the wearables during the operations. Collectively, these features enable continuous, real-time health monitoring, providing valuable data for the early detection of health issues and enhancing the overall situational awareness in various applications, from everyday wellness to emergency response scenarios.

Table 1: Open Datasets explored in our work

Risk Type	Dataset	Sensor Type
Stress Level	WESAD [22]	ECG, EDA, EMG, TEMP
Stress Level	SWELL [9]	HRV
Dehydration	Dehydration Dataset [19]	Bioimpedance, Salivary, TEMP

In our analysis, we present two explanations provided by SHAP, in order to illustrate the differences in feature importance for predicting health risks. In Figure 3, the first explanation, derived from a dehydration dataset, highlights that bioimpedance measurements significantly impact the model’s decisions. However, obtaining bioimpedance measurements typically requires specialized equipment, making it challenging to implement and measure with generic wearable devices. In contrast, the second explanation, based on the SWELL stress detection dataset, utilizes features and measurements extracted from HRV. Unlike bioimpedance, HRV is relatively easy to measure with standard wearable sensors, making it more practical for widespread use in real-time health monitoring. This comparison underscores the importance of selecting accessible and reliable features for effective health risk prediction in wearable technology.

Apart from the feature importance explanations provided by SHAP and LIME, we can also provide explanations using global surrogate models. While local surrogate models can be trained and used through the LIME technique, global surrogate models can also be utilized to provide explanations to the user. These models aim to globally approximate the behavior of the complex Random Forest models that were used in the previous analysis. For instance, we

(a) Measuring dehydration levels (total body water loss)

(b) Measuring work stress levels

Fig. 3: Comparison of SHAP values in two different datasets, used to identify the most important features for each medical condition.

Table 2: Explanations using rules, for two samples in different risk types

Risk Type	Rule	Prediction	Truth
Stress Level	(MEDIAN_RR = 842.49) > 739.49 and (MEAN_RR = 824.84) > 819.6 and (SDRR_RMSSD = 10.01) > 5.12	Level 1	Level 1
Dehydration	(impedance right leg = 2.65) > -1.21 and (salivary cortisolone = -1.64) < 0.8 and (temperature right hand = 0.3) > 0.25	0.33	0.36

create a simple decision tree model with a depth level equal to 3 as a surrogate model for each of the two previous use cases, training it using the predictions of the black box model as a reference. The surrogate model can then intrinsically generate feature importance weights at a global level, while also providing

rule-based explanations at a local level. These rule-based explanations show how each individual prediction is made in an easy-to-understand manner to the user, using logic. This is inherent to decision trees, since their decisions are made by following a path from the tree root up to the tree leaves.

Examples for rule-based explanations provided for the two use cases are shown in Table 2. In each case, three input features are compared to threshold values to form the final rule. In the stress detection example, HRV related features are used, while in the dehydration example, features related to bioimpedance, salivary, and body temperature measurements are used. The surrogate model correctly predicts the stress level in the first scenario, while also outputting a prediction close to the actual water loss measurement in the second scenario.

Table 3: A set of questions for preliminary analysis and post testing assessment towards the users of the explainability tool

Preliminary Analysis	Post – Testing Assessment
1. Evaluate your general trust in an AI system and its outputs.	1. How often did you need additional clarification beyond what the AI system provided?
2. Would an explanation provided alongside an AI decision increase your trust in the model?	2. Assess the usefulness of the AI explanations.
3. Are there any scenarios or tasks where understanding the AI’s reasoning is critical for you? If yes, please describe.	3. Assess your satisfaction with the AI explanations.
4. How familiar are you with wearable technology used for health risks monitoring?	4. Assess to what extent the AI explanations contributed to your decision-making process.
5. What explanation type do you believe would be useful to you (visual, text, rule, etc.)?	5. How effective were the AI predictions in identifying stress, exhaustion, and dehydration among team members?
6. Which vital signs and health indicators do you consider most critical during emergency operations?	6. Did the application help in reducing the response time and improving the overall efficiency of the team?
7. How valuable would real-time data fusion from multiple sensors be in improving situational awareness?	

To further enhance usability and ensure first responders can quickly understand AI predictions and reasoning, our tool also converts feature importance weights provided by SHAP or LIME for each health risk into natural language explanations. Through this transformation, users receive clear, concise descriptions of the most important features influencing each prediction, instead of having to

understand and interpret complex graphs. For example, the tool might output, "*Heart rate variability significantly impacts stress prediction, and is easily monitored by your wearable device,*" or "*Skin temperature variations are crucial for assessing dehydration risk.*". These explanations will compile in real-time and will be provided to the user alongside the prediction of the Machine Learning algorithms.

The final step of our proposed approach is the evaluation of the explainability tool that was developed as part of our work. In order to assess the effectiveness and usability of the generated explained alerts, we plan to conduct user evaluations through questionnaires provided to first responders and healthcare professionals, focusing on both preliminary as well as post-testing analysis. The goals of the preliminary analysis are to identify possible bottlenecks in the first responders' work that could be improved or solved through our tool, assess their familiarity with AI systems and wearables, and measure their trust in such systems. On the other hand, the post-testing assessment will be conducted after the integration of the tool is completed, aiming to measure the overall effectiveness of the tool, the satisfaction of the users with the provided explanations, and identify future steps for improvement. A sample questionnaire for user evaluation can be seen in Table 3.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

In conclusion, this paper has detailed the development of an advanced Explainable AI complementary tool, aimed to be integrated in a platform tailored for first responders, which will leverage real-time data from wearables to predict and monitor health risk. For our study, various open datasets were used for testing both Machine Learning as well as XAI algorithms, with the focus being on highlighting important features that will help first responders in making decisions. For this first iteration, we examined the use of SHAP, LIME, and surrogate models, in order to generate the explanations. A continuous feedback loop with users is a necessity, in order to improve the system based on real-world use cases, as well as agree on the best and clearest visualization approach for the provided explanations.

Regarding future work, we plan to enhance the user-friendliness of our explanations by integrating the output with Large Language Models. This integration will allow for more natural and interactive explanations, bringing the complex information generated by the XAI system closer to the human perspective. Secondary avenues of work that we would like to explore are additional model-agnostic techniques in the medical domain, as well as explanation generation for images retrieved from cameras, which are commonly utilized by first responders for enhanced situational awareness.

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